

ISSUES OF YOUTH SPIRITUALITY DEVELOPMENT THROUGH OUR NATIONAL MUSIC ART

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola yoshlar ma’naviyatini yuksaltirishda musiqa san’atining ahamiyati va musiqa terapiyasi haqida yozilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Musiqa terapiyasi, art terapiya, musiqiy ta’lim, yuksak ma’naviyat, Yunus Rajabiy, Komiljon Otaniyozov, Olim Komilov, honandalik.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье написано о значении музыкального искусства и музыкотерапии в воспитании духовности молодежи.

Ключевые слова: Музыкотерапия, арт-терапия, музыкальное образование, высокая духовность, Юнус Раджаби, Комильджон Отаниёзов, Олим Комилов, пение.

ABSTRACT

This article is written about the importance of music art and music therapy in raising the spirituality of young people.

Key words: Music therapy, art therapy, musical education, high spirituality, Yunus Rajabi, Komiljon Otaniyozov, Olim Komilov, singing.

In the years of independence, in addition to great creative works, significant changes in the fields of culture and art are clearly visible in our country. It is always in the center of our country’s attention that the growing young generation, our youth, become healthy, educated, cultured and well-rounded individuals in all aspects, and have a spiritually rich and broad worldview. The effective use of traditional music has a special place in the education and moral development of the young generation. The goal of musical education is to raise the young generation to become a perfect person who can deeply understand our national musical wealth and inherit our national musical heritage, who is aware of and respects not only their own national traditions, but also the culture of other nations. The fact that every home of the Uzbek people has a dutor, circle or other national musical instrument is a sign of our national musical

heritage. When we listen to them, our hearts are filled with pleasure, and our emotions are more excited. Music has an important role in improving human education, as well as giving spiritual nourishment to a person. That is why the tones that touch the delicate strings of the human language do not sound for nothing. We cannot imagine the development of our musical heritage without the great figures of our art, such as Haji Abdulaziz Abdurasulov, Usta Olim Komilov, Uzbek musicologist academician Yunus Rajabi, who created the unique methods of the teacher-apprenticeship school.

The services of teachers in passing our traditional songs from generation to generation are worthy of praise. The role of educational institutions is incomparable in helping our children, who are our future, become well-rounded children who contribute to the development of our society, contribute to the development of the country, and use the opportunities created for them. The longevity of traditional folk songs, the purity of their spiritual and moral intention, and the unity of musical tones. Human experiences, meaning and requests in them are full of thoughts, vital and sincere, so they give pleasure to the listener and cheer him up. Songs of such spiritual beauty have become a wonderful and immortal tradition of folk music. Also, traditional folk songs are distinguished by their simplicity, folk-like form, rich meaning and elegance of images. Researching the importance of traditional folk music in the formation of human spirituality leads to the following conclusions. As the traditional folk music is passed from generation to generation over centuries, in this process it becomes rich and embodies the thoughts, pains, dreams and wisdom of the people. With its traditionality, simplicity and greatness, impressiveness, richness of many artistic heritages, it has become not only the favorite art form of the nation, but also an important form of ethnocultural studies. Using the educational opportunities of traditional music is still an important task in forming a well-rounded person; The historically tested scope of folk music is much wider:

a) spiritual, b) aesthetic; c) educational; g) educational opportunities play an important role in the spiritual development of a person and give good results; Ceremonial music, which is considered a rich source of spiritual influence, influences the formation of morals and national way of life. , girl's oshi, nikoh, wedding, various rituals and yoryars, lapars, argumentation, throwing coins, showing a mirror, opening the face, greeting the bride and groom, etc.: Religious ceremonies: Bibi Sheshanba, Bibi Mushkulkushad, making sacrifices, iftar mourning (rituals, etc.) are of great importance; Ritual music is also an artistic and aesthetic source. Many folklore genres that are part of rituals have become a unique basis for the formation of modern art. All folk art that is performed or used works help to form the artistic and aesthetic thinking of listeners, spectators and participants; Musical works participating in ceremonies are educational methods of the traditional process, command, example, example, advice,

training, appeal, irony, criticism, criticism , approval, as well as artistic-aesthetic resources, dramatic situations, exchange of experience, and ideological aspects necessary in the processes of skill formation as educational tools; The masterpieces of the nation's spiritual culture are collected in the traditional folk music, which is of great importance in the development of national consciousness and self-awareness in the current period of independence. The study of our national music, songs, traditions and rituals passed down from generation to generation is of particular importance nowadays.

If samples of them are taught more widely and in detail in schools, higher and secondary special education institutions, and if they are included in the curriculum, we will be able to preserve them and pass them on to the next generation, as well as interest young people in our rich national musical heritage. we were in conclusion, one of the important tasks is to increase interest and love for our national musical heritage, to create a foundation for musical practice, and to form national pride among young people. At the same time, musical education nurtures human qualities and develops a number of vital skills in the young generation, including important qualities such as perception and sensitivity, agility and enthusiasm, creativity and creativity.

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